

Short communication

New distributional data for nine interesting Old World burrower bug species (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Cydnidae)

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Abstract. New records for nine burrower bug species (Hemiptera: Pentatomoidea: Cydnidae) are provided. Three species, *Stibaropus indonesicus* (Cephalocteinae: Scaptocorini), *Garsauria aradoides* (Garsauriinae), and *Pseudoscoparipes kinabalensis* (Cydninae: Geotomini), are recorded for the first time from Brunei. *Chilocoris piceus* representing the tribe Cydnini of the subfamily Cydninae, and two species belonging to the tribe Geotomini of this subfamily, namely *Adrisa romani* and *Pseudoscoparipes fraterculus* are new to Thailand. Two Afrotropical species, i.e., *Chilocoris laevicollis* (Cydninae: Cydnini) and *Aethus holothrix* (Cydninae: Geotomini) are reported for the first time from Kenya and Namibia, respectively. In addition, the occurrence of *Lactistes obesipes* in Australia has been confirmed.

Key words: true bugs, Pentatomoidea, distribution, new country records, Australia, Borneo, Brunei, Kenya, Namibia, Thailand, Oriental Region, Afrotropical Region.

The 'Morphology and Molecules in Animal Systematics' research laboratory at the Institute of Biology (University of Opole) has been collecting alcohol-preserved specimens representing different taxonomic groups of true bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) for many years. During the preparation of specimens from the family Cydnidae for use in molecular studies (Lis J. A. & Domagała, *in press*), the presence of several species was documented for countries where their occurrence had not previously been reported. In addition, one specimen was found in the material analysed, confirming the presence of burrower bug species on a continent where its occurrence was previously considered doubtful.

The exact details of the specimens of these species, their voucher numbers and the accession numbers of their sequences deposited in the GenBank database, are given below. All specimens were identified to species by the first author.

Cephalocteinae: Scaptocorini

Stibaropus indonesicus J.A. Lis

Stibaropus indonesicus J.A. Lis, 1991: 320.

Material examined: BRUNEI, Tutong, 4°45'49.65"N 114°35'56.23"E, mangrove forest, shrimp farm area, MV light on road, before rain, 21.X.2014; 6-9 pm, leg. C. Damken, 1 ex.

Distribution (Lis J. A. 1991, 1994, 1999): Indonesia (Java, Sumatra, Sulawesi). **New to Brunei and Borneo.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_218Ssp; GenBank accession number: OR691659.

Garsauriinae

Garsauria aradoides Walker

Garsauria aradoides Walker, 1868: 536.

Material examined: BRUNEI, Pulau Selirong FR, 4°52'57.42"N 115°8'13.80"E, Mangrove forest, bridge over creek, MVP light, no rain, 22.VII.2014, 6 pm - 4 am, leg. C. Damken, 1 ex.

Distribution (Lis J. A. 1992, 1993, 1994, 1999): Moluccas, Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, Indonesia (Java, Sumatra, Buru, Ambon, Irian Jaya), Malaysia (Sarawak). **New to Brunei.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_217Ga; GenBank accession number: OR691647.

Cydninae: Cydnini

Chilocoris laevicollis Horváth

Chilocoris laevicollis Horváth, 1919: 259.

Material examined: KENYA, Narok district, Loita Hills: Mburobudi Hills, 4 km S-E Entasekera (220m), 1° 52,789 S - 35°52,288 E, 7-13.XI.2012, leg. L. Bartolozzi, A. Bandinelli, S. Bambi, F. Fabiano, I. Ranz, 1 ex.

Distribution (Britton 1940; Medler 1980; Linnavuri 1977, 1980, 1993; Lis J. A. 1999; Robertson 2009; Krüger & Lis 2019; Lis B. & Lis J.A. 2016): Central African Republic, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Liberia,

Nigeria, Republic of the Congo, Sudan, Tanzania. **New to Kenya.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_3Cl; GenBank accession number: OR691642.

***Chilocoris piceus* Signoret**

Chilocoris piceus Signoret, 1884: 518.

Material examined: THAILAND, Nakhon Ratchasima, Sakaerat Environmental Research Station SERS, 14°30'N, 101°55'E, 400 m, light trap, 21-26 Sep 2013, A. Wolski & T. Yasunaga leg., 1 ex.

Distribution (Atkinson 1887; Distant 1902; Hsiao et al. 1977; Lis J. A. 1999): China (Hainan, Sichuan, Yunnan), India, Malaysia (Malaya), Sri Lanka. **New for Thailand.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_8Cp; GenBank accession number: OR691643.

Cydninae: Geotomini

***Adrisa romani* J. A. Lis**

Adrisa romani J. A. Lis, 1994: 129.

Material examined: THAILAND, Nakhon Ratchasima, Sakaerat Environmental Research Station SERS, 14°30'N, 101°55'E, 400 m, light trap, 21-26 Sep 2013, A. Wolski & T. Yasunaga leg., 1 ex.

Distribution (Lis 1994, 1999): Known only from Malaysia (Malaya), so far. **New for Thailand.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_10Ar; GenBank accession number: OR691631.

***Aethus holothrix* Linnavuori**

Aethus holothrix Linnavuori, 1977: 37.

Material examined: NAMIBIA, Khomas Region, Trans Kalahari Inn, 22°32'52,3"S 17°16'39,2"E, 22 km E of Winthoek, 16.11.2014, 1918 m, at light, leg. R. Dobosz, 1 ex.

Distribution (Linnavuori 1977, 1980, 1989, 1993; Linnavuori & van Harten 1997, 2002; Lis J. A. 1991, 1999; Robertson 2009): Ghana, Sudan, Yemen. **New to Namibia.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_24Ah; GenBank accession number: OR691632.

***Lactistes obesipes* Signoret**

Lactistes obesipes Signoret, 1879: 234.

Material examined: AUSTRALIA, Northern Territory, Humpty Doo 15-8-2018, leg. Laurie Cookson, 1 ex.

Distribution (Lis J.A. 1996, 1999; Lis J.A. & Lis B. 2008): China (Guangdong). The species was originally described from "New Holland". However, due to the possibility of its lectotype being mislabelled, it was removed from the Australian Cydnidae faunal list (Lis J.A. & Lis B. 2008). The present record confirms the occurrence of the species in Australia.

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_14Lo; GenBank accession number: OR691648.

***Pseudoscoparipes kinabalensis* J. A. Lis**

Pseudoscoparipes (Aethiellus) kinabalensis J.A. Lis, 1994: 256.

Material examined: BRUNEI, Temburong NP, Ulu Ulu Ressort, helipad, forest edge, banana plant, litter, 14.III.2015, 3-3:30 pm, leg. C. Damken, 4°33'17.3" N 115°9'14.3"E, 1 ex.

Distribution: Malaysia (Sabah). **New to Brunei.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_219Pk; GenBank accession number: OR691657.

***Pseudoscoparipes fraterculus* J. A. Lis**

Pseudoscoparipes (Aethiellus) fraterculus J. A. Lis, 1994: 254.

Material examined: THAILAND, Sakaerat, dry tropical forest, at light, 11-22.04.2013, leg. M. Mazur & A. Wolski, 1 ex.

Distribution (Lis J.A. 1994, 1999): Hitherto known only from Vietnam. **New for Thailand.**

Voucher data: UO sample number: UO_20Pb; GenBank accession number: OR691656.

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